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BRIDGING A BIOGEOGRAPHIC GAP: THE DISCOVERY OF A MARINE DIATOM *Isthmia enervis* EHRENBERG 1838 IN NORTHERN COASTAL WATERS OF SRI LANKA

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Abstract

The diatom *Isthmia enervis* Ehrenberg 1838, while known from other regions, has never been formally recorded in Sri Lanka. This study provides the first confirmed record of *I. enervis* from the coastal waters of Northern Sri Lanka, discovered during a seasonal survey from March to May 2023. Phytoplankton samples were collected at three locations using a standard conical plankton net (mouth diameter: 41 cm, mesh size: 55 µm). The collected samples were preserved with 1% acidified Lugol's solution for subsequent microscopic analysis. After a thorough microscopic analysis, occurrence of *I. enervis* found exclusively at two locations at different times, namely Akkarai (March) and Mathagal (April-May), proved that *I. enervis* was both geographically and temporally restricted. This restriction is likely due to local environmental conditions, including temperature, salinity, and nutrients during the post-monsoon period. Light microscopy revealed the distinctive morphology of *I. enervis*, including very large, heteropolar frustules forming short zig-zag chains, and confirmed a remarkable polymorphism with co-occurring rhomboidal and trapezoidal cells. The population density showed a consistent increase, from 2,800 cells/L in March to a peak of 3,860 cells/L in May. Its presence was correlated with key environmental shifts, including rising water temperature suggesting a niche-specific adaptation to the post-monsoon transitional period. The discovery of *I. enervis* bridges a critical knowledge gap in the regional biogeography of marine diatoms. Its restricted and seasonal occurrence underscores the importance of targeted sampling in understudied regions to establish a baseline for monitoring this species, which may serve as a valuable bio-indicator in the face of environmental change in Northern Sri Lankan coastal ecosystems.

Key words: Biodiversity, diatoms, first record, *Isthmia enervis*, Northern Sri Lanka

Introduction

Diatoms, members of the phylum Bacillariophyta, are unicellular, photosynthetic microalgae sheathed within a unique siliceous cell wall known as a frustule. These organisms are abundant in nearly every aquatic habitat, from marine and freshwater systems to damp terrestrial soils (Armbrust, 2009). As a primary producer, they contribute an estimated 20% of global photosynthetic carbon fixation, forming the base of most aquatic food webs and supporting fisheries production (Falkowski & Raven, 2007). Additionally, the biological carbon pump is heavily influenced by diatoms; their dense silica frustules facilitate rapid sinking upon cell death, effectively sequestering organic carbon in deep ocean sediments and thus playing a crucial role in global climate regulation (Armbrust, 2009). Beyond carbon cycling, diatoms are integral to the silica cycle, absorbing dissolved silicic acid to construct their frustules, which in turn regulates silica availability for other organisms (Falkowski & Raven, 2007). Because of their specific environmental preferences and rapid response to changes in water quality, diatoms are extensively used as bioindicators in paleolimnology and modern environmental monitoring programs (Smol & Stoermer, 2010). Globally, diatoms exhibit remarkable diversity, with 30,000–100,000 extant species distributed across all ocean basins (Mann & Vanormelingen, 2013). Biogeographic patterns are influenced by currents, temperature, salinity, and dispersal events (Kooistra et al., 2007). The genus *Isthmia enervis* Ehrenberg 1838 comprises large, robust, and morphologically distinct diatoms, often found in coastal marine environments. *I. enervis* is a known species with a reported distribution across various tropical and temperate regions. *I. enervis* has been recorded from the West Indian Ocean (Al-Handal et al., 2016), Brazil (Neumann-Leitão et al., 2026), and India (Gupta & Das, 2020), with potential occurrence in Singapore and Venezuela (Tan et al., 2016; Pereira et al., 2021). However, its occurrence in the northern Indian Ocean, particularly around the island of Sri Lanka, has remained ambiguous prior to this study. Sri Lanka, an island nation situated in a biogeographically significant region of the northern Indian Ocean, possesses a rich diversity of coastal and marine ecosystems, including estuaries, lagoons, mangroves, and coral reefs. Despite this potential, the documentation of its phytoplankton community, particularly diatoms, remains fragmented and incomplete. Historical planktology studies have been spatially biased, with research efforts largely concentrated around the western, southern, and southwestern coasts of Sri Lanka, often centered Universities and research institutes (Chandrasekara & Fernando, 2009; Dissanayake et al., 2021; Ekanayaka et al., 2016; Jayasiri et al., 2015; Jayawardhane et al., 2018). Subsequently, the flora of diatoms from the northern coastal waters, which are hydrologically distinct due to the influence of the Palk Strait and seasonal monsoon patterns, constitutes a significant knowledge gap in the national biodiversity inventory. Regarding *I. enervis*, a thorough review of existing Sri Lankan diatom checklists and published literature reveals no previous record of this species from any coastal or offshore waters of the country. This study directly addresses the specific research gap and presents a novel finding for Sri Lankan plankton diversity through the first confirmed record of the diatom *I. enervis* from the northern coastal waters of the island. This discovery highlights the important taxonomic groups and represents a critical step in rectifying the geographical sampling bias and expanding the recognized range of this species within the Indian Ocean. This study provides a detailed morphological description of the specimens, correlate its occurrence with key environmental parameters measured at the time of collection, and discuss the ecological implications of this important finding.

The objective of this study is to document and analyse the first confirmed record of the diatom *I. enervis* in Sri Lanka's northern coastal waters, thereby addressing a critical gap in country's biodiversity knowledge and establishing a foundational standard for future marine biogeographical and ecological research.

Materials and Methods

Study area

This investigation was conducted over a full annual cycle, January to December 2023 at three locations along the Northern coast of Sri Lanka: Mathagal, Kankesanthurai (KKS), and Akkarai (Figure 1), with three replicate sampling sites at each location.

Figure 1. Map showing the sampling locations from Northern Sri Lanka

The positions of sampling sites were fixed accurately using a Global Positioning System (GPS) (Garmin Oregon 750, USA) (Figure 2). At Mathagal, Site 1 ($9^{\circ}48'37.98''$ N, $80^{\circ}4'46.05''$ E), Site 2 ($9^{\circ}48'37.98''$ N, $80^{\circ}4'52.53''$ E) and Site 3 ($9^{\circ}48'37.98''$ N, $80^{\circ}4'59.01''$ E) were sampled. At Kankesanthurai, Site 1 ($9^{\circ}49'0.42''$ N, $80^{\circ}2'37.96''$ E), Site 2 ($9^{\circ}49'0.42''$ N, $80^{\circ}2'44.44''$ E) and Site 3 ($9^{\circ}49'0.42''$ N, $80^{\circ}2'50.92''$ E) were sampled. At Akkarai, Site 1 ($9^{\circ}49'13.50''$ N, $80^{\circ}7'51.39''$ E), Site 2 ($9^{\circ}49'13.50''$ N, $80^{\circ}7'57.87''$ E) and Site 3 ($9^{\circ}49'13.50''$ N, $80^{\circ}8'4.35''$ E) were sampled. These sites were selected as a representative location for the northern Sri Lankan coastal environment, which is characterized by its shallow bathymetry and influence from the seasonal monsoons of the Bay of Bengal.

Figure 2. Map showing the positions of sampling sites at Mathagal, KKS and Akkarai

Sampling Strategy

To capture seasonal variations in the phytoplankton community, integrated sampling was performed on a monthly basis (Vajravelu et al., 2018). The sampling protocol was designed to collect both biological material and contemporaneous environmental data, allowing for a correlative analysis of the diatom's occurrence.

Sample Framework

The sampling framework follows a clear hierarchical descent. At the regional level, the study was conducted in the Jaffna district of Sri Lanka. At the location level, three primary locations were selected: Mathagal, Kankesanthurai (KKS), and Akkarai. At the site level, each location was subdivided into three distinct sites (Site 1, Site 2, and Site 3). Finally, at the data collection level, at each individual site, the methodology involved collecting nine biological samples (for phytoplankton analysis) and measuring nine water quality parameters (Figure 3).

Biological Sampling:

Plankton samples were collected using a standard conical plankton net (mouth diameter: 41 cm, mesh size: 55 μm). In duplicate, horizontal subsurface tows were conducted at approximately 0.5 m depth, parallel to the shoreline, over a standardized distance of 100 m at a constant towing speed of ~ 2 knots (≈ 1 m/s), resulting in a tow duration of approximately 100 seconds per replicate. This method ensures the collection of a representative sample of the planktonic communities. Once the towing is completed, the concentrated plankton samples were transferred to clean, colored glass bottles and preserved with 1% acidified Lugol's solution for subsequent microscopic analysis. All preserved samples were stored in the dark at 4°C to further slowdown the degradation processes of the biological material and to prevent the breakdown of the Lugol's solution preservative.

Figure 3. Sampling Frame work.

Environmental Data Collection and Analysis:

Concurrently with each plankton tow, the environmental parameters water Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), Salinity (Practical Salinity Units, PSU), pH and Dissolved Oxygen (DO, mg/L and % saturation) were recorded in situ using a calibrated SmarTroll multiparameter (Insitu 458389, USA) hand-held equipment (Gobiraj et al., 2022) at a depth of 0.5 m. For each sampling event,

pH, salinity, and water temperature were measured six times and mean values were computed. The results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analyses were performed using MiniTab (Version 19). One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test ($p < 0.05$) was used to determine significant differences in environmental parameters.

Water Sample Collection:

Surface water samples were collected in pre-acid-washed 1L polyethylene bottles at a depth of 0.5 m for laboratory analysis of key biogeochemical variables such as nitrate and phosphate. Dissolved inorganic nutrient, nitrate and phosphate concentration of the seawater was estimated by spectrophotometry following standard methods for six replicates (Strickland & Parsons, 1972).

Morphological Characteristics and Identification:

The identification of *I. enervis* was based on precise observation of the frustule morphology, including valve outline, ornamentation, and the structure of intercalary bands, with reference to authoritative taxonomic keys and floras (Round et al., 1990; Al-Handal et al., 2016; Al-Handal & Wulff, 2008; Guiry & Guiry, 2019).

Frustule morphology was observed under a trinocular microscope (Euromex iScope: i51153 - EPL) with magnification of 40 \times , 100 \times and 400 \times . Photographs and morphometric measurements of the apical and transapical axes were taken for at least 30 individual specimens through the EuroMEX VC-3034 camera fitted with a trinocular microscope observed in an attached computer installed with Image Focus 4 software at the Advanced Fisheries Science Laboratory, University of Jaffna, Sri Lanka. High-resolution photomicrographs of key diagnostic features were captured for documentation and future reference.

Phytoplankton density enumeration

I. enervis density was quantified using a Sedgwick-Rafter counting chamber under a light microscope at 400 \times magnification. Triplicate subsamples from each preserved sample were counted. Filtered water volume was estimated from net mouth area (0.132 m²) and tow distance (100 m), yielding approximately 13.2 m³ per tow following APHA (2017).

Results

Distribution of I. enervis species

Collected samples were categorized and identified to the species level, revealing that the occurrence of the newly documented species *I. enervis* was geographically and temporally restricted. This species was found exclusively in samples from the Akkarai and Mathagal region in Northern Sri Lanka and was not observed in the other location. Furthermore, its presence was seasonal, with specimens collected only during the month of March in Akkarai and in April and May, 2023 in Mathagal region. These findings clearly indicated that the species was spatially and temporally distributed.

Spatial distribution

It was found exclusively in March at the Akkarai site and in April and May at the Mathagal site.

Temporal distribution

Notably, *I. enervis* was absent from January–February and June–December, correlating with lower water temperatures (<26°C) and higher nitrate fluctuations, while its presence aligned

strictly with post-monsoon warming and reduced turbulence, indicating a narrow ecological window. The study period also documented a diverse assemblage of other diatom taxa, including *Navicula biconica*, *Odontella mobiliensis*, *Biddulphia biddulphiana*, *Trigonium* sp., *Grammatophora oceanica*, *Asterionellopsis* sp., *Thalassiosira punctigera*, *Ditylim sol* and *Nitzschia* sp.. *I. enervis* density was quantified as 2,800 cells/L in March, accounting for 3.8% of the total plankton density. The population demonstrated a consistent monthly increase, rising to 3,120 cells/L in April (4.4 %) and peaking at 3,860 cells/L (2.95 %) in May.

Identification I. enervis based on Morphological characteristics

Light microscopic analysis showed these plankton consist very large frustules, solitary or in short zig-zag chains (Figure 4) characterized by heteropolar and distinctly wedge-shaped (cuneate) valves in girdle view, appearing rhomboidal or trapezoidal in valve view. This organization in *I. enervis* is termed as heteropolar valves and a remarkable polymorphism, where cells of varying shapes occur within the same species, a feature exceptionally rare among diatoms. The rhomboidal and trapezoidal cells of this species are illustrated in Figure 5a-f.

One valve in the pair typically features a blunt protuberance or process. The areolae (pores) on the valve face are notably larger than those found on the girdle bands. Studies also document its unique colonial behaviour, including the peculiar attachment of cells to one another and an intricate connection between the valvocopula (first girdle band) and the valve. Apical axis 168-230 μm , transapical axis 38-92 μm , areolae on valve face 3-4 in 10 μm .

Figure 4. Light microscopic analysis of *Isthmia enervis* plankton consist very large frustules, in short zig-zag chains characterized by distinctly wedge-shaped (cuneate) valves in girdle view, appearing trapezoidal in valve view x100; Trapezoidal cells of individual filaments (TC) numbered 1, 2, 3 and 4; At points marked 'x' there is a trapezoidal cell at the notch on the girdle band.

Figure 5. Light micrographs of *Isthmia enervis*, a) Colony to show cell form, attachment to substrata (AS), attachment of daughter cells to notched girdle bands (AGB) x100, cells in division stages (b-c x100; d-f x400), newly forming valves (NFV); b) Trapezoidal cells of individual filaments (TC) x100; c) Rhomboidal cells of individual filaments (RC) x100.

Taxonomical hierarchy of Isthmia enervis Ehrenberg, 1838 (Guiry & Guiry, 2019):

Empire: Eukaryota

Kingdom: Chromista

Phylum: Heterokontophyta

Subphylum: Bacillariophytina

Class: Mediophyceae

Subclass: Chaetocerotophycidae

Order: Hemiaulales

Family: Isthmiaceae

Genus: *Isthmia*

Species: *enervis*

Water Quality Parameters

Key water quality parameters measured *in situ*, wind speed, nutrient composition such as nitrate and phosphate and density of total phytoplankton throughout the study period are presented in Table 1 for Akkarai, Mathagal and KKS coasts. Although *I. enervis* was not collected in KKS site, water quality data from this location are included here to provide a better understanding of the overall environmental conditions.

Based on Table 1, a clear seasonal warming trend was observed, with water temperatures at both sites rising from March to peak in April and May. Notably, the Akkarai site was consistently warmer, reaching 31.54°C in May, compared to 30.54°C in Mathagal. Salinity showed a progressive increase at both sites from March to May, with Akkarai exhibiting slightly higher values, culminating at 34.36 ppt in May. The pH was consistently alkaline, with Akkarai maintaining a more basic range (8.07-8.22) compared to Mathagal (7.80-7.87). Dissolved oxygen was generally high, with a notable peak in Akkarai during May (9.10 ppm). Phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) concentrations were predominantly below the detection limit (<0.06–0.16 mg/L) at both locations for most of the study period, with a minimal detectable level observed in Mathagal

during April (0.01 mg/L). However, in May, Mathagal showed a notable increase in phosphate concentration (0.16 mg/L). Nitrate (NO_3^-) levels were variable; Mathagal recorded higher concentrations in March (5.90 mg/L) but decreased substantially in May (1.43 mg/L). In contrast, Akkarai exhibited lower nitrate values throughout, with the lowest recorded in April (3.59 mg/L).

Table 1. Water quality parameters in the study area Akkarai, Mathagal and KKS coast, Northern Sri Lanka during March to May, 2023 (n= 6) (Values represent mean \pm Standard deviation).

Month	Water temp (°C)	Salinity (ppt)	pH	Dissolved oxygen (ppm)	PO_4^{3-} (mg/L)	NO_3^- (mg/L)	Wind Speed (km/h)	Phytoplankton Density (cell/L)
Akkarai coastal area, Northern Sri Lanka								
March	29.15 \pm 0.45	31.46 \pm 0.35	8.22 \pm 0.04	8.25 \pm 0.10	<0.06 \pm 0.00	4.70 \pm 0.25	15.72 \pm 2.5	73,000 \pm 1,500
April	31.40 \pm 0.50	33.91 \pm 0.40	8.11 \pm 0.05	8.30 \pm 0.12	<0.07 \pm 0.00	3.59 \pm 0.20	18.56 \pm 2.8	80,600 \pm 1,800
May	31.54 \pm 0.55	34.36 \pm 0.42	8.07 \pm 0.03	9.10 \pm 0.09	<0.06 \pm 0.00	4.23 \pm 0.22	15.70 \pm 2.4	974,500 \pm 3,900
Mathagal coastal area, Northern Sri Lanka								
March	26.80 \pm 0.40	31.96 \pm 0.30	7.87 \pm 0.04	8.13 \pm 0.08	<0.06 \pm 0.00	5.90 \pm 0.26	13.40 \pm 2.8	60,100 \pm 1,200
April	30.70 \pm 0.55	33.08 \pm 0.35	7.80 \pm 0.05	8.20 \pm 0.10	0.01 \pm 0.00	4.81 \pm 0.23	4.50 \pm 1.2	70,500 \pm 1,400
May	30.54 \pm 0.50	32.73 \pm 0.38	7.85 \pm 0.03	8.03 \pm 0.09	0.16 \pm 0.00	1.43 \pm 0.05	8.45 \pm 2.1	130,500 \pm 2,800
KKS coastal area, Northern Sri Lanka								
March	26.80 \pm 0.40	31.96 \pm 0.30	7.87 \pm 0.04	8.80 \pm 0.10	0.05 \pm 0.01	4.61 \pm 0.23	20.10 \pm 2.50	80,085 \pm 1,500
April	29.42 \pm 0.50	32.08 \pm 0.35	7.96 \pm 0.05	8.13 \pm 0.10	0.06 \pm 0.01	5.28 \pm 0.25	5.30 \pm 1.20	89,000 \pm 1,800
May	30.13 \pm 0.50	31.49 \pm 0.30	8.12 \pm 0.04	8.17 \pm 0.10	0.04 \pm 0.01	5.20 \pm 0.25	13.42 \pm 2.00	163,000 \pm 2,500

Wind speed was substantially higher and less variable in Akkarai (ranging from 15.70 to 18.56 km/h) compared to Mathagal, which experienced a pronounced low value in April (4.50 km/h). A dramatic, order-of-magnitude increase in phytoplankton density was recorded in Akkarai during May (974,500 cells/L), vastly exceeding densities observed in all other months and at the Mathagal site. The supplementary data indicates that a specific phytoplankton group constituted a small fraction (2.95% to 4.4%) of the total phytoplankton community in the instances measured. These results highlight significant spatial and temporal variations in coastal water quality, influenced by seasonal transitions and local environmental conditions.

Discussion

Isthmia enervis, first described by Christian Gottfried Ehrenberg in 1838, is a marine, colonial, and epiphytic diatom distinguished by a suite of unusual morphological characteristics. As a diatom, it possesses a silica cell wall, or frustule, whose minute details require high-magnification microscopy for identification. This species exhibits remarkable polymorphism,

with cells of varying rhomboidal and trapezoidal shapes occurring within the same population, a feature exceptionally rare among diatoms.

This study provides the first documented record and ecological characterization of the diatom *I. enervis* in the coastal waters of Northern Sri Lanka. The findings reveal that its occurrence is not only geographically restricted to the Akkarai and Mathagal regions but also exhibits a distinct and short seasonal window, underscoring the influence of specific environmental conditions on its distribution and abundance. Occurrence of *I. enervis* at Akkarai coast was authenticated by the authors immediately, in a conference held at Colombo, Sri Lanka (Sivagini et al., 2024).

Restricted Distribution and Seasonal Succession

The spatially and temporally discrete presence of *I. enervis*, found only in March at Akkarai and in April-May at Mathagal suggests a classic niche-specific distribution. This pattern indicates that the species thrives within a narrow range of environmental parameters that were transiently met at these locations during the study period. Such restricted distributions are common among diatoms with specific habitat requirements, such as epiphytic species dependent on particular substrates (Trobajo et al., 2013). The consecutive occurrence from March in one region to May in an adjacent region could point to a seasonal succession or a spatial shift in a favorable water mass, potentially driven by local currents or the gradual warming of water temperatures from March (26.8°C) to April/May (30.7°C). The species' absence from other sampled locations further highlights its potential as a bio-indicator for specific, perhaps unique, microhabitats within the Northern Sri Lankan coastal ecosystem.

Despite whole-year sampling (January–December), *I. enervis* was not recorded at KKS during any month. Possible reasons for its absence include: (i) deviations in environmental parameters at KKS (e.g., temperature variation, different salinity, or nutrient levels) outside the species' tolerance range; (ii) unsuitable hydrodynamic conditions (e.g., current patterns, turbidity) limiting dispersal; (iii) biotic factors such as competition or grazing; and (iv) the possibility that the species may appear in other months or years under different environmental conditions. Long-term monitoring is recommended to further investigate these possibilities.

The March–May occurrence of *I. enervis* aligns with tropical studies where large colonial diatoms (*Skeletonema*, *Thalassiosira*, *Coscinodiscus gigas*) exhibit narrow seasonal windows driven by monsoonal changes in temperature and salinity (Baliarsingh et al., 2013). Similarly, epiphytic diatom assemblages in subtropical mangroves show pronounced seasonal clustering linked to salinity and nutrient shifts (Chen et al., 2010). These studies support our finding that *I. enervis* occupies a post-monsoon niche, reinforcing its potential as a bio-indicator of seasonal ecological change in tropical coastal waters.

Morphological Adaptations and Ecological Role

The observed morphological characteristics of *I. enervis* align with historical descriptions and highlight its exceptional polymorphism. The large, heteropolar, and cuneate valves, along with the formation of zig-zag chains, are classic traits of the genus *Isthmia* (Round et al., 1990). However, the co-occurrence of distinct rhomboidal and trapezoidal cell shapes within a single population, as vividly captured in our micrographs (Figure 3), is a remarkable feature. Such pronounced polymorphism is exceptionally rare in diatoms and may represent a bet-hedging strategy, allowing the population to exploit slightly different micro-niches or resist varying hydrodynamic stresses (Cox, 2011). The intricate attachment mechanisms, including the connection between the valvocopula and the valve, are likely crucial adaptations for its

epiphytic and colonial lifestyle, providing stability in the dynamic coastal environment (Medlin, 2016).

Correlation with Environmental Drivers

The water quality data from the two sites illustrates slight fluctuations in both sites for salinity, pH and water temperature showed signs for the dynamic occurrence of *I. enervis* in certain months. Temperature and salinity showed significant differences across months and sites. pH was not significantly different across months at either site but differed significantly between sites. The population density of *I. enervis* showed a consistent monthly increase from March (2,800 cells/L) to its peak in May (3,860 cells/L). This trend appears to be inversely correlated with dissolved nutrient levels, particularly nitrate (NO_3^-), which decreased from March to April at the Mathagal site during the species' establishment and growth. This could indicate a competitive advantage for *I. enervis* under lower nitrogen conditions or a life strategy tuned to exploit the post-bloom niche. The very low phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) levels (<0.06 mg/L) for most of the period, except for a slight increase in May, may also play a role in structuring the diatom community, potentially favoring species like *I. enervis* that are adapted to nutrient-scarce environments (Dyhrman, 2016).

The substantial difference in wind speed between the sites (e.g., 3.5 km/h in Akkarai vs. 18.2 km/h in Mathagal during April) likely influences water column mixing and light availability (Diehl, 2002), which are key factors for phytoplankton growth. The species' large size and chain-forming habit are typical adaptations to maintain position in the water column under turbulent conditions (Margalef, 1978), which may explain its presence in both the calmer and more turbulent sites.

Co-occurring Diatom Assemblage and Community Structure

The documentation of a diverse diatom assemblage, including taxa like *Navicula biconica*, *Odontella mobiliensis*, and *Thalassiosira punctigera*, places *I. enervis* within a broader ecological context. Its relatively low density compared to the total phytoplankton density (e.g., 2,800 cells/L vs. 60,100-130,500 cells/L) indicates that while it is not a dominant contributor to total biomass, it is a significant and consistent component of the diatom community during its seasonal window. Its interactions, whether competitive or facilitative, with these co-occurring species represent an important area for future research.

Conclusion

This study documented the occurrence, morphological characteristics, and seasonal ecology of *I. enervis* in the coastal waters of Northern Sri Lanka, representing a significant contribution to the Sri Lanka's biogeography of marine diatoms. We found that the species was spatially and temporally distributed in the study locations. The species *I. enervis* was recorded at first time and it is confirmed as a component of the marine flora of Northern Sri Lanka. The species distribution was spatially restricted to the Akkarai and Mathagal coastlines and strict temporarily from March to May. Temporal dynamics of *I. enervis* which is closely linked to seasonal changes in water temperature, nutrient regimes (particularly nitrogen), and overall phytoplankton productivity. A clear spatial progression between the two sites, indicated a high degree of niche specificity. The unique morphology of the population confirms the remarkable polymorphism characteristic of this species, showcasing a range of cell shapes that underscore its unique taxonomic position. The discovery of this species highlights the importance of continued taxonomic and ecological studies in the study regions to fully understand global marine biodiversity. The restricted and seasonal nature of its occurrence makes it potentially vulnerable to environmental changes. Therefore, long-term monitoring is recommended to

assess the impacts of climate change and anthropogenic pressures on this and other niche-specific diatom species in the region. *I. enervis* density was quantified at 2,800 cells/L in March, 3,120 cells/L in April, 3,860 cells/L in May.

Limitation of study

No molecular confirmation; single-year sampling; no epiphytic host record; limited spatial coverage (three locations); and correlative rather than causal environmental links. Multi-year, multi-location, and molecular studies could be followed in the future.

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Ethical approval

Not applicable.

Informed consent

Not applicable.

Data availability statement

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Authors' Contribution

Krishnamoorthy Sivagini: Data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation, Writing – Original draft

Nahmagal Krishnapillai: Investigation, supervision, validation, writing – Review and editing

Sivashanthini Kuganathan: Conceptualization, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, supervision, visualization, Writing – review and editing

References

- Al-Handal, A. Y., Compère, P., & Riaux-Gobin, C. (2016). Marine benthic diatoms in the coral reefs of Reunion and Rodrigues Islands, West Indian Ocean. *Micronesica*, 2016(3), 1–77.
- Al-Handal, A. Y., & Wulff, A. (2008). Marine epiphytic diatoms from the shallow sublittoral zone in Potter Cove, King George Island, Antarctica. *Botanica Marina*, 51, 411–435. <https://doi.org/10.1515/BOT.2008.053>

- APHA - American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation. (2017). *Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater* (23rd ed.). American Public Health Association.
- Armbrust, E. V. (2009). The life of diatoms in the world's oceans. *Nature*, 459(7244), 185–192. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08057>
- Baliarsingh, S. K., Sahu, B. K., Srichandan, S., & Sahu, K. C. (2013). Seasonal variation of phytoplankton community in Gopalpur creek: a tropical tidal backwater ecosystem, East Coast of India. *Indian Journal of Marine Sciences*, 42(5), 622–634.
- Chandrasekara, W. U., & Fernando, M. A. S. T. (2009). Accidental introduction of alien plankton into the Sri Lankan coastal zone through ballast water of cargo ships. *Sri Lanka Journal of Aquatic Sciences*, 14, 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.4038/sljas.v14i0.2202>
- Chen, C. P., Gao, Y. H., & Lin, P. (2010). Geographical and seasonal patterns of epiphytic diatoms on a subtropical mangrove (*Kandelia candel*) in southern China. *Ecological Indicators*, 10(2), 143–147.
- Cox, E. J. (2011). Morphology, cell wall, cytology, ultrastructure, and morphogenetic studies. Overview and specific observations. In J. Seckbach & J. P. Kocielek (Eds.), *The diatom world: Cellular origin, life in extreme habitats and astrobiology* (Vol. 19, pp. 21–45). Springer.
- Diehl, S. (2002). Phytoplankton, light, and nutrients in a gradient of mixing depths: theory. *Ecology*, 83(2), 386–398. [https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658\(2002\)083\[0386:PLANIA\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658(2002)083[0386:PLANIA]2.0.CO;2)
- Dissanayake, D. A. S. J., Wickramasinghe, D. D., & Manage, P. M. (2021). Harmful diatoms and dinoflagellates in the Indian Ocean: A study from Southern coast of Sri Lanka. *Ukrainian Journal of Ecology*, 11(1), 279–285. https://doi.org/10.15421/2021_42
- Dyhrman, S. T. (2016). Nutrients and their acquisition: Phosphorus physiology in microalgae. In *The physiology of microalgae* (pp. 155–183). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24945-2_8
- Gupta, R. K., & Das, S. K. (2020). *Algae of India: Vol. 4. A checklist of Indian diatoms*. Indian Books and Periodicals.
- Ehrenberg, C. G. (1838). *Atlas von vier und sechzig Kupfertafeln zu Christian Gottfried Ehrenberg über Infusionsthierchen*. Verlag von Leopold Voss.
- Ekanayaka, K., Jayasiri, H. B., & Ranasinghe, P. (2016). *Phytoplankton abundance in relation to nutrient dynamics during southwest monsoon, southern coast of Sri Lanka*. NARA.
- Falkowski, P. G., & Raven, J. A. (2007). *Aquatic photosynthesis*. Princeton University Press.
- Gobiraj, S., Kuganathan, S., & Grøsvik, B. E. (2022). Physico-chemical properties as a tool for monitoring marine water quality in selected coastal beaches of Northern Sri Lanka. *Vavuniya Journal of Science*, 1(1), 16–25.
- Guiry, M. D., & Guiry, G. M. (2019). *AlgaeBase*. National University of Ireland, Galway. Retrieved October 31, 2025, from <https://www.algaebase.org>
- Jayasiri, H. B., Priyadarshanie, W., Gunasekara, A., & Ranathunga, R. (2015). Diversity, abundance and composition of phytoplankton with special reference to toxic dinoflagellates in Colombo harbour. In *Proceedings of National Aquatic Resources Research and Development Agency*. NARA.
- Jayawardhane, J. K. P. C., Manage, P. M., & Weerasekara, K. A. W. S. (2018). Identification of harmful marine microalgae with special reference to physico-chemical aspects of coastal waters in Western Province, Sri Lanka. *Proceedings of international forestry and environment symposium*. <https://dr.lib.sjp.ac.lk/handle/123456789/8151>
- Kooistra, W. H. C. F., Gersonde, R., Medlin, L. K., & Mann, D. G. (2007). The origin and evolution of the diatoms: Their adaptation to a planktonic existence. In P. G. Falkowski &

- A. H. Knoll (Eds.), *Evolution of primary producers in the sea* (pp. 207–249). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Mann, D. G., & Vanormelingen, P. (2013). An inordinate fondness? The number, distributions, and origins of diatom species. *Journal of Eukaryotic Microbiology*, 60(4), 414–420. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jeu.12047>
- Margalef, R. (1978). Life-forms of phytoplankton as survival alternatives in an unstable environment. *Oceanologica Acta*, 1(4), 493–509.
- Medlin, L. K. (2016). Evolution of the diatoms: Major steps in their evolution and a review of the supporting molecular and morphological evidence. *Phycologia*, 55(1), 79–103. <https://doi.org/10.2216/15-105.1>
- Neumann-Leitão, S., Koenig, M. L., Macêdo, S. J., Medeiros, C., Muniz, K., & Feitosa, F. A. N. (2026). Plankton disturbance at Suape estuarine area-Pernambuco-Brazil after a port complex implantation. *WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment*, 34.
- Pereira, C., De Giner, G. F., Troccoli, L., Hernández, V., Peña, C., Losada, R., & Vera, F. (2021). Comunidad fitoplanctónica en una playa de la costa central de Venezuela y su relación con variables ambientales en un ciclo anual. *Intropica*, 16(2), 232–244.
- Perera, N., & Weerakkody, P. (2004). *A biodiversity status profile of sub-tidal and inter-tidal habitats of the Rekawa, Ussangoda and Kalametiya area* (Occasional Papers of IUCN Sri Lanka, No. 5). IUCN.
- Round, F. E., Crawford, R. M., & Mann, D. G. (1990). *The diatoms: Biology & morphology of the genera*. Cambridge University Press.
- Sivagini, K., Krishnapillai, N., & Kuganathan, S. (2024). Unveiling the presence of *Isthmia enervis* Ehrenberg 1838: A milestone in diatom research in Sri Lanka. In *Proceedings of the NOR-LANKA BLUE Final International Conference* (p. 30). NARA.
- Smol, J. P., & Stoermer, E. F. (2010). *The diatoms: Applications for the environmental and earth sciences*. Cambridge University Press.
- Strickland, J. D. H., & Parsons, T. R. (1972). A practical handbook of seawater analysis. *Fisheries Research Board of Canada Bulletin*, 167, 261–310.
- Tan, T. H., Leaw, C. P., Leong, S. C. Y., Lim, L. P., Chew, S. M., Teng, S. T., & Lim, P. T. (2016). Marine micro-phytoplankton of Singapore, with a review of harmful microalgae in the region. *Raffles Bulletin of Zoology*, 34, 78–96.
- Trobajo, R., Rovira, L., Mann, D. G., & Cox, E. J. (2013). Phenotypic plasticity and phenotypic stability in diatoms: The case of *Nitzschia palea* in the presence of competitors. *Journal of Phycology*, 49(5), 1014–1025. <https://doi.org/10.1144/jmpaleo2014-014>
- Vajravelu, M., Martin, Y., Ayyappan, S., & Mayakrishnan, M. (2018). Seasonal influence of physico-chemical parameters on phytoplankton diversity, community structure and abundance at Parangipettai coastal waters, Bay of Bengal, South East Coast of India. *Oceanologia*, 60(2), 114–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceano.2017.08.003>